

Librarians' Awareness and Competencies on Data Creation and Storage Processes for Research Data Management Services in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

Introduction: This study investigates librarians' awareness and competencies on data creation and storage processes for Research Data Management (RDM) services in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria. The research was guided by two key objectives.

Method: The study employed quantitative approach using multi-stage sampling technique to select federal university libraries across the Northern Nigeria. Respondents comprised of 213 professional librarians working in these six federal university libraries. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection and the data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics through frequency, percentage distribution, mean, and standard deviation.

Result/Findings: The analysis revealed that librarians generally have a high level of awareness on data creation processes, with a mean awareness score of 3.01 (on a 4-

point scale). Most librarians (74.7%) indicated being highly aware of how data is created in various formats, and 80.1% acknowledged understanding data storage solutions such as cloud systems and repositories. However, awareness of metadata schemas and data documentation standards remained relatively low, indicating areas requiring further training. Regarding competencies in data storage, the study established librarians have strong general data storage competencies (mean = 3.21), but lower proficiency in managing institutional repositories (mean = 2.70) and research-specific databases such as MySQL and PostgreSQL (mean = 2.93).

Conclusion: The study concludes that while librarians in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria have a solid foundation in RDM-related activities, continuous professional development, structured training programs and institutional policy implementation are necessary to bridge existing knowledge and skill gaps.

Recommendations: The study recommends addressing challenges related to technical deficiencies in metadata handling, advanced data descriptions, research-specific repositories, and databases management skills. These will enhance librarians' capacity to support researchers, improve institutional RDM services, and ensure long-term data preservation and accessibility.

Keywords: Librarians, Awareness, Competencies, Data Creation & Storage, Research Data Management, University Libraries

Introduction

Research Data Management (RDM) services in academic libraries provide essential support to researchers, assisting with various stages of the data lifecycle, from creation and storage to accessibility. These services help faculty, staff, and students to create data management plans (DMPs), establish metadata standards, find and cite data, deposit data in repositories, and foster collaborative efforts. Generally, RDM services offered by libraries are classified into two main categories: informational or consultative services and technical services.

Informational or consultative services focus on providing researchers with guidance on developing data management plans, understanding metadata standards, and finding resources for data citation and storage. Librarians also create web guides to aid in data discovery and assist researchers in collaboration. Technical services, on the other hand,

involve direct assistance in preparing data for repository deposit, identifying data eligible for storage, transforming metadata, and even collaborating on projects as team members. When institutional storage infrastructure is lacking, librarians can recommend self-deposit in open-access repositories like Dryad, Figshare, or zenodo, where data can be shared more broadly. In European countries, RDM services sometimes extend to distributed networks and embedded services, where librarians are actively involved in tasks like verifying metadata, file formats, and archiving protocols, thereby ensuring quality control (Matusiak and Sposito, 2018).

A critical aspect of RDM services is the Data Management Plan (DMP), a formal document outlining the handling of data during and after research. Increasingly, funding agencies and institutions require DMPs as part of grant applications to ensure data will be properly managed. A well-prepared DMP clarifies data collection, storage, and accessibility protocols and anticipates long-term data preservation needs, making it easier for researchers to structure their data effectively. However, many researchers need support in creating these plans, and librarians are well-positioned to provide this assistance. By guiding the development of DMPs, librarians support researchers through the entire data lifecycle.

The data lifecycle in research is segmented into data creation, storage, and accessibility, each step plays a crucial role in effective data management. Data creation encompasses the generation of digital, computer-readable, or paper-based data collected during research activities. According to the University of Galway (2024), data creation involves gathering raw data through methods like surveys, experiments, or observations. Researchers, as the primary creators, are responsible for crafting a data blueprint, detailing how data will be collected, processed, and stored. This blueprint forms part of the DMP, streamlining the research process and ensuring data is managed efficiently. Librarians contribute to data creation by assigning metadata, enhancing data discoverability and reusability. They also advise on data documentation and file formats, ensuring data compatibility and accessibility over time. In this way, librarians indirectly participate in data creation, ensuring that data is organized and accessible to other researchers within and outside the institution.

Once research data is created, it is essential to store it securely and efficiently to ensure long-term preservation, accessibility, and reliability. The selection of suitable storage systems is of critical importance because storage options differ in their security capabilities as well as scalability and performance features. The most commonly used

storage systems for managing research data include cloud-based storage system that allows institutions to store and access their data remotely via the internet. For instance, Google Drive and Dropbox represent cloud storage systems while OneDrive, AWS, Google Cloud Storage, and Microsoft Azure serve as additional examples. Others are High-Performance Computing (HPC) Storage designed for handling large-scale computational research projects that require high processing power and fast data transfer rates (HPE, 2023).

Data repositories and archives are dedicated storage platforms designed to preserve research data for future use, often following FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. The repositories provide mechanisms to maintain data in an organized manner while ensuring it remains easy to search and use. Examples include: University-based Institutional Repositories like DSpace, Fedora, and Dataverse serve as platforms where researchers store and share their datasets. National and Global Repositories encompass government-funded or large-scale archives like Dryad Digital Repository, Zenodo, and Figshare which provide open storage and sharing options for research datasets.

There is also local storage system known as on-premises storage that involves keeping data on physical devices within an institution or research facility. This option provides greater control over data security but may require additional maintenance and backup measures. A good example of this are dedicated servers, external hard drives, flash drive, and so on. So, choosing the right storage system depends on several factors and conditions. But using a combination of these storage systems, will allow institution and researchers to protect their data while ensuring that it remains useful for future use and reuse. Therefore, effective data storage involves robust infrastructure and secure protocols, including backup and recovery systems. Dataworks (2022) highlights that efficient storage strategies safeguard data integrity, prevent data loss from technical failures, and protect against cybersecurity threats. Universities are responsible for providing adequate storage infrastructure, both in terms of physical systems and technical support, to help researchers manage data effectively. For librarians to provide this, they need to be aware of and have the necessary proficiency research data management.

Awareness of research data management among librarians will create a supportive environment for implementing data services in academic libraries. Providing guidance on best practices in data creation, storage, and preservation for researchers, has put librarians more especially in advanced world at the forefront of ensuring integrity,

accessibility, and usability for a long time. When librarians are informed about research data management, they will be able to educate the researchers about ways to structure their data, use metadata, and other storage solutions that might afterwards lead to better organization and reuse of data. Also, an informed librarian, knowledgeable in the storage of data, will be able to manage and curate research outputs in institutional repositories so as to maintain the security and access of data.

Librarians' awareness on data creation and storage enables them organize workshops and awareness campaigns and also promote best practices for handling research data. Though, many librarians lack the technical knowledge necessary for data curation, analysis, and infrastructure development Mushi, *et al.* (2020). Fostering their skills basically in the areas of metadata, data ethics and, equally so, digital preservation will engage them toward adequately offering RDM services. The paradigm shift in librarianship forced librarians acquire new skills such as data management skills. Data librarianship clearly sets out the need to gain more specialized skills pertaining to data governance, visualization, and intellectual property rights, allowing libraries to act as the center to support RDM. By bettering the knowledge of librarians on data creation and storage, libraries are positioned to give better support to research communities, ensuring compliance with data policies, and raising visibility and impact of institutional research.

When it comes to effective research data management (RDM) in libraries, the skills and competencies of librarians also play a crucial role. It is important for librarians to have a solid foundation of data curation, metadata, policy development, and the latest technology in this digital age. Librarians need a diverse set of skills to help researchers manage their data effectively. They need to have data curation and metadata skills, this will enable understand how to organize, preserve, and index data for easy retrieval. They must be proficient in technical and I.T skill to enable them manage digital repositories, storage systems, and security measures. It also important to have legal and ethical knowledge in order to assist researchers complying with data policies, licensing agreements, and intellectual property rights. Engaging and collaborating with researchers, policymakers, and tech experts is key to successful RDM services in academic libraries that librarians need to possess.

Unfortunately, research shows there are librarian's lack of awareness and competencies on data creation and storage (Adamu, *et al.*, 2024). The specific areas where the research gap exists on data creation is the extent to which librarians are knowledgeable/awareness about different data creation formats, standards, and best practices is unclear. Librarians

also lack practical skills or competencies for assisting researchers with data creation, such as using data management tools and planning data collection. Equally, researchers might not be aware of the library's role in data creation, potentially hindering librarians' involvement in the research process.

To bridge this knowledge gap, universities and funding organizations should invest in continuous training for librarians through workshops, online courses, and hands-on experiences Ohaji *et al.* (2019). This kind of training programs should be customized to meet the specific needs of each institution and may cover areas such as metadata and Indexing focusing on helping with data organization and retrieval. Institutional repository management training that facilitating data storage and access. Data literacy and research support that guide researchers on best practices for handling data. Emerging RDM Technologies that will keep librarians informed about the latest digital tools and data science applications. Although, there are other several open-access platforms that provide specialized RDM free online training programs for librarians like MANTRA which provide training on data management planning, security, and preservation.

Statement of the Problem

In today's fast-changing world of academic research, data has become an invaluable resource, making effective Research Data Management (RDM) services in university libraries more important than ever. Federal university libraries are expected to assist researchers with everything from data creation to storage and management. However, how well these services work often hinges on the librarians' understanding and skills in dealing with research data. Even with the growing focus on Open Science and data-driven research, many university libraries find it tough to establish strong RDM services due to lack of skilled and awareness among librarians.

Research shows that while librarians are generally knowledgeable about traditional information management, many lack specialized expertise needed for data creation and storage (Adamu, *et. al*, 2024). On daily basis, researchers and students from different departments or units used to data creation in different form and formats in the course of their academic activities. These data used to be left un-identified and un-processed leading to various inefficiencies, such as data loss, inadequate data preservation, and difficulties in data sharing and reusing.

To bridge this knowledge gap therefore, it is essential to assess librarians' level of awareness and skills in data creation and storage in order to identify the challenges they face, and suggest strategies for building their capacity so that federal university libraries effectively support research data management.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. determine librarians' level of awareness on data creation process in relation to research data management services in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria;
2. ascertain librarians' competencies on data storage process in relation to research data management services in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria;

Literature Review

Research, an inherently data-driven process, generates vast amounts of data in various formats every day. Research data includes any information collected, generated, or created to validate research findings, spanning formats like documents, laboratory notebooks, and digital databases (Abduldayan, 2020). Research data may include spreadsheets, audio or video files, methodologies, or simulation software data, emphasizing the diversity and complexity of research outputs (University of Leeds, 2023). Given this complexity, research data management (RDM) plays a critical role in organizing, securing, and preserving data across its lifecycle. RDM entails activities and practices that facilitate data planning, documentation, storage, and accessibility to ensure data remains usable over time (Abduldayan, 2020). Effective RDM involves various stakeholders and requires comprehensive planning and the establishment of institutional standards to guide researchers in managing their data from creation through storage to disposal.

Creating awareness about RDM is essential for both researchers and librarians. Awareness initiatives can enhance understanding among university stakeholders about the importance and benefits of RDM practices. Mushi *et al.* (2020) found that awareness of RDM practices is low among researchers at the University of Dodoma, highlighting a need for targeted awareness campaigns. Both researchers and university stakeholders need greater exposure to RDM concepts to support effective data handling and

preservation. Abduldayan *et al.* (2018) suggest that universities implement training and workshops to strengthen data management skills for librarians and to promote best practices across the academic community.

For librarians to offer comprehensive data management services, they must develop a wide range of competencies and knowledge. Hamad *et al.* (2019) stress the importance of educating librarians on RDM services to meet emerging demands. While librarians may already possess experience in managing traditional library materials, Newton *et al.* (2010) emphasize that they often require further training in building institutional data repositories and managing digital datasets.

Ohaji *et al.* (2019) outline essential RDM competencies, such as data curation, policy formulation, metadata management, and collaborative partnership skills. However, a skills gap persists in areas like technical proficiency and information management. Masinde *et al.* (2021) found that university librarians often lack specific RDM skills, underscoring the need for capacity-building programs. These programs should aim to improve technical and data-handling competencies, providing ongoing professional development and supporting emerging RDM trends (Abduldayan *et al.*, 2018).

Addressing training needs in RDM involves identifying gaps in librarians' skills and knowledge. Ohaji *et al.* (2019) argue that data librarians require specialized professional development to meet evolving research data service demands. Identifying researchers' needs and RDM requirements helps in designing targeted training for prospective data librarians, focusing on areas like data organization, metadata schema, and institutional repository usage. Online training tools can also provide accessible resources to support librarians and researchers in developing RDM competencies (Alex-Nmecha and Onifade, 2022). Hence, universities must prioritize research data management by equipping librarians with essential skills, creating awareness among researchers, and fostering an environment of data protection and accessibility.

Methodology

This study adopted cross-sectional survey research design. This approach was chosen because it allows for data collection at a single point in time, enabling the study of many subjects quickly and cost-effectively and it can be applied in the behavioural, health, and social sciences, especially in multidisciplinary settings and complex situational or societal research (George, 2023). The population of this study comprised of 213 professional

librarians working in different federal university libraries. Multi-stage sampling technique was used in selecting the sample size of the study. Total enumeration was used in selecting all the professional librarians. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire. Descriptive statistics through the use of table, frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used for data analysis.

Result and Discussions

This chapter presents the data collected through the use of the questionnaire instrument distributed to the target respondents from selected federal universities in Northern Nigeria. It consists of research questions, demographic data of the respondents, and analysis of sections using frequency counts and percentages, mean, standard deviation analysis and discussions of findings as analysed from the information obtained from the questionnaire instrument: data collected were analysed using IBM SPSS Version 23.0.

Response rate

A total of 213 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to targeted respondents in six (6) selected federal universities in Northern Nigeria. Table 4.1 presented the response rate of the respondents.

Table 1: Response rate

S/N	Response Rate	Frequency	Percentages
Number of Questionnaire Administered		213	100%
Returned Questionnaire		166	77.9%
Un-returned Questionnaire		47	22.1%
TOTAL		213	100%

However, 166 copies of the questionnaire were correctly filled and returned. This gave a response rate of 77.9% which is adequate for analysis of data and making inferences while un-returned questionnaire were 47 representing 22.1%.

Demographic data of the respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents captured from the study area included: name of the university library, gender distribution, designation, educational

qualification and years of working experience of the respondents, were analysed in this section using the simple descriptive statistical analysis.

Table 2: Demographic Distribution

S/N	Variables	Response	Frequency	Percentage s
1	Name of University Library	Abdullahi Fodiyo Library Complex	32	19.3
		Bayero University Library	40	24.1
		Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Library Complex	19	11.4
		Ramat University Library	40	24.1
		University Library, Federal University Kashere	17	10.2
		University of Jos Library	18	10.8
		TOTAL	166	100%
2	Gender	Male	127	76.5
		Female	39	23.5
		TOTAL	166	100%
3	Designation	Assistant Librarian	30	18.1
		Deputy University Librarian	3	1.8
		Higher Library Officer	6	3.6
		Librarian I	33	19.9
		Librarian II	20	12.0
		Principal Librarian	16	9.6
		Principal Library Officer I	7	4.2
		Principal Library Officer II	4	2.4
		Senior Librarian	36	21.7
		Senior Library Officer	9	5.4
		University Librarian	2	1.2
		TOTAL	166	100%
4	Educational Qualification	First Degree	41	24.7
		Postgraduate Diploma	4	2.4
		Professional Masters	7	4.2
		Master's Degree	81	48.8
		Ph.D	33	19.9
TOTAL	166	100%		
5	Working Experience	1 - 5 years	40	24.1
		6 - 10 years	45	27.1
		11 - 15 years	62	37.3
		16 - 20 years	13	7.8
		21 and above	6	3.6
		TOTAL	166	100%

Table 4.1 showed the demographic distribution of the respondents. Table 4.1 revealed that, there are various designations represented among the federal university libraries, with a relatively balanced distribution among different carders. The librarians possessed different high level of degrees and this suggest a well-educated workforce with potentially in-depth knowledge and expertise toward research data management service. While on the librarians working experiences, the largest group of librarians have 11-15 years of experience, forming a solid core of mid-career professionals with valuable knowledge and expertise. But, the newly recruited librarians with 1-5 years of experience, highlight a potential need for mentorship and training programs to ensure smooth integration and knowledge transfer.

Table 3: Librarians’ level of awareness on data creation for research data management services in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria (N=166)

S/N	Statements	HA=4 Freq. (%)	A=3 Freq. (%)	LA=2 Freq. (%)	NA=1 Freq. (%)	F \bar{x}	\bar{x}	SD
1	I am aware of how data are being created in different formats (e.g. text documents, spreadsheets, graphics).	47(28.3)	77(46.4)	36(21.7)	6(3.6)	497	2.99	0.80
2	I am aware of how data are being created in different forms (e.g. doc. sav. ppt. jpeg.).	38(22.9)	90(54.2)	34(20.5)	4(2.4)	494	2.97	0.73
3	I am aware of how researchers and students generate their data.	37(22.3)	73(44.0)	52(31.3)	4(2.4)	475	2.86	0.78
4	I am aware of how to locate generated data.	35(21.1)	98(59.0)	33(19.9)	0(0)	500	3.01	0.64
5	I am aware of how to process created data for future and reuse.	33(19.9)	87(52.4)	42(25.3)	4(2.4)	481	2.89	0.73
6	I am aware of how to offer guidance on data documentation standards e.g. creating metadata for data storing and sharing.	23(13.9)	87(52.4)	52(31.3)	4(2.4)	461	2.78	0.70
7	I am aware of how produced data are properly proof read and cross checked before release.	71(42.8)	78(47.0)	17(10.2)	0(0)	552	3.33	0.65

8	I am aware on how to use data storage solutions like servers, repositories and cloud system for data storage.	74(44.6)	80(48.2)	12(7.2)	0(0)	560	3.37	0.61
9	I am aware of how to identify created data appropriate for repositories.	47(28.3)	85(51.2)	34(20.5)	0(0)	511	3.08	0.69
10	I am aware of various metadata schemas like Dublin Core and Darwin Core.	23(13.9)	85(51.2)	54(32.5)	4(2.4)	459	2.77	0.71
11	I am aware of how to file and classify generated data for easy use.	42(25.3)	85(51.2)	39(23.5)	0(0)	501	3.02	0.70
Decision mean = 2.50								

Source: *Field Survey (2023)*

Note: N=166, HA = Highly Aware, A = Aware, LA =Lowly Aware, NA = Not Aware. Retrieved, N= Number of Questionnaire Retrieved, \bar{X} = Mean, SD= Standard Deviation. Decision – weighted average = 3.01.

The weighted average mean is 3.01 while decision benchmark rule is 2.50. This means that any score above 2.50 reflects a high level of awareness, while scores below 2.50 indicate a low level of awareness. Table 4.2 revealed that out of the eleven items listed on librarians' level of awareness on data creation for research data management services in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria; all the items produced mean scores which were above the average decision benchmark of 2.50. The finding with highest mean scores of 3.37 revealed that, librarians are awareness of storage solutions (e.g., servers, repositories, and cloud storage), which means they are very familiar with digital storage methods. Many librarians understand how to check and verify data before sharing it (Mean = 3.33). Librarians have a high understanding of data that fits in repositories (Mean = 3.08) and organizing created data (Mean = 3.02). So they have a good sense of data organization for retrieval and reuse. Librarians also have high (Mean = 3.01) understanding how to find created data, process the data for reuse (Mean = 2.89), and provide guidance on metadata creation (Mean = 2.78). But understanding of metadata schemas like Dublin Core and Darwin Core is lower (Mean = 2.77) showing a gap in their technical know-how. Most librarians know a lot about how people make data in different formats (Mean = 2.99) and forms (Mean = 2.97). They also understand how researchers and students create data (2.86).

This implies that, librarians in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria are generally aware of data creation processes but require additional training in metadata standards, documentation, and classification. Solving these challenges will enhance librarians' ability to

support researchers in data management, storage and accessibility thereby improving RDM services in university libraries.

Table 4: Librarians' competencies on data storage for research data management services in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria. (N=166)

S/N	Statements	VC=4 Freq. (%)	C=3 Freq. (%)	SC=2 Freq. (%)	NC=1 Freq. (%)	F \bar{x}	\bar{x}	SD
1	I have the ability to store data in a external hard drives, portable or high-capacity storage for backups and large data datasets.	30(18.1)	102(61.4)	28(16.9)	6(3.6)	488	3.13	0.70
2	I have the ability to use cloud-based storage systems like Google drive, Dropbox, Microsoft OneDrive to save research data.	41(24.7)	75(45.2)	42(25.3)	8(4.8)	481	3.21	0.82
3	I am proficient enough in using research-specific cloud platforms like figshare, zenodo, and dryad to store and share data.	27(16.3)	71(42.8)	60(36.1)	8(4.8)	449	3.12	0.79
4	I have expertise in using desktop, laptop storage, internal hard drives or SSDs for active research data.	30(18.1)	91(54.8)	39(23.5)	6(3.6)	477	2.87	0.73
5	I am proficient in operating institutional repository (e.g. DSpace, Dataverse or EPrints) for data storing and sharing.	60(36.1)	84(50.6)	20(12.0)	2(1.2)	534	2.70	0.69
6	I have the ability in using metadata or data catalogs systems like CKAN and	49(29.5)	83(50.0)	27(16.3)	7(4.2)	506	2.70	0.79

	DataCite for data organization and documentation.								
7	I can confidently use MySQL, PostgreSQL, NoSQL, or Graph databases for data storage.	51(30.7)	91(54.8)	20(12.0)	4(2.4)	521	2.93	0.71	
	Decision benchmark: 2.50								

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Note: N= 166, VC = Very Competent, C = Competent, SC =Somewhat Competent, NC = Not Competent at all, Retrieved, N= Number of Questionnaire Retrieved, X=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation. Decision - weighted average = 2.96.

The weighted average mean is 2.96, while the decision benchmark is 2.50. This means that any score above 2.50 reflects a high competency, while scores below 2.50 indicate a low competency. Table 4.3 revealed that out of the seven items listed on the competencies possessed by librarians on data storage for research data management services in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria; all the items produced a mean scores above the benchmark of 2.50. The finding with highest mean scores of 3.21 revealed that, most librarians demonstrated high competency in using cloud-based storage systems such as Google Drive, Dropbox, and Microsoft OneDrive. They also have high competency in storing data on external hard drives and high-capacity storage devices (Mean = 3.13). Librarians showed relatively lower competency in using research-specific cloud platforms like Figshare, Zenodo and Dryad (Mean = 3.12), which means there is need for further training in specialized research repositories. Also, proficiency in institutional repositories (e.g. DSpace, Dataverse EPrints) was reported as high but not excellently (Mean = 2.70), indication room for further improvement in managing institutional digital archives. Similarly, librarians have moderate competency in using metadata or data catalog systems such as CKAN and DataCite for data organization (Mean = 2.70), which means while librarians are aware of metadata tools, their practical application in managing and documenting research data requires improvement. The librarians' ability to use MySQL, PostgreSQL, NoSQL, and Graph databases for data storage was rated as high competency (Mean = 2.93), which indicate a reasonable level of technical expertise in database management. But however, database skills still require further reinforcement, as a considerable percentage of librarians rated themselves as only somewhat competent.

This implied that, while librarians in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria have strong general data storage competencies, there lack metadata management, research-specific repositories, and databases management skills. Improving on these through training, policy development and institutional support will increase librarians' ability to manage research data effectively.

Summary of the Findings

1. The findings of the study showed that librarians generally have high level of awareness on data creation processes in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria.
2. The analysis of the findings also established that librarians have strong general data storage competencies in federal university libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Conclusion:

This study examined librarians' awareness and competencies on data creation and storage processes for research data management (RDM) services in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. Librarians are being evaluated to cover the level of awareness on data creation stage and existing competency of librarians on data storage as they pertain to RDM services. The study conclude that, librarians have an adequate level of awareness on data creation processes, demonstrating their knowledge on how research data are generated, formatted and structured for effective management. This awareness is crucial in enabling librarians to guide researchers in best practices for structuring, documenting, and preserving research data. However, technical deficiencies in metadata handling and advanced data descriptions need to be addressed. Similarly, the study established that librarians possess strong general competencies in data storage, particularly in using external storage devices and cloud-based platforms. However, competencies in research-specific repositories, metadata management, and advanced database systems require further strengthening to enhance their role in supporting research data preservation and accessibility. Thus, Federal University libraries will have to institute capacity-building programs to improve the technical competence of librarians' role in producing better research data management practices.

Recommendations:

1. There is need for continuous professional development, targeted training, and policy implementation among Federal university libraries to bridge existing knowledge gaps.
2. Federal university libraries should invest in capacity-building initiatives to enhance librarians' technical expertise in research-specific data storage and metadata management.

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